

FUNDAMENTALS OF ORNAMENTAL PLANT PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

In the infrastructure of our cities there are rare and rare species such as ginkgo biloba, tulip tree, cypress. Also, ornamental shrubs decorate the squares of our cities: camel, biota, budleya, siren, kanna, yukka and others. It should be noted that among the ornamental plants we find many species of medicinal, essential oils, honey.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the independent Republic of Uzbekistan has established all-round ties of friendship and cooperation with the world community. As an equal member of the United Nations, our republic is a party to all international agreements and conventions and is committed to all good deeds in the future. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has announced a nationwide Green Space project. The project plans to plant 200 million trees and shrubs a year. Trees absorb harmful carbon dioxide from the air, produce oxygen instead, and help us breathe. They provide coolness in the heat, protecting the environment from noise. 25 "green zones" and alleys will be created in Tashkent 111 kilometers of 28 canals flowing through the city will be strengthened and parks will be created. Ornamental trees will also be planted along

60 kilometers of canals and 250 kilometers of sidewalks in the capital [1, 2, 3].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

It is estimated that there are about 3 trillion trees in the world today. However, every minute, an equal part of their 27 football fields is being cut. During the "One Million Trees" campaign in 2019-2020, a total of about 3.8 million bushes of fruit and ornamental trees were planted in all regions of Uzbekistan. At the new stage of development of our country, as in all areas, the work being done to protect the environment, rational use of natural resources, prevent the negative impact of environmental problems on human health is a guarantee of sustainable development. Of course, the legal basis for these reforms is enshrined in our Constitution.

In particular, Article 50 of the Constitution states that "Citizens are obliged to treat the environment with care." This requires the

rational use of land, water, forests, mineral resources, fauna, flora and other natural resources, their restoration and protection, as well as the timely fulfillment of this obligation. This fact is clearly reflected in all laws in the field of ecology, which further strengthens the constitutional requirements.

Articles 54, 55 and 100 of the Basic Law also entrust legal entities and individuals with the task of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources. On the basis of these constitutional norms, more than thirty laws and about three hundred legal acts on ecology, environment, protection of public health and rational use of natural resources have been adopted.

We believe that under the leadership of our esteemed President, Uzbekistan has a worthy place in the world and is ready to solve any problems. In addition, the plants that are considered our "Green Friends", especially ornamental species, have an immense social and hygienic value. They release phytoncides from more deciduous species, killing viruses and bacteria that spread various diseases in the atmosphere. That is, it helps prevent the spread of disease among our people. It is also worth noting that many plants neutralize and neutralize various gases emitted into the atmosphere from factories.

Therefore, it is not in vain that a good proverb has been invented among the people. Indeed, our lush and uniquely beautiful and attractive plants and flowers have a positive effect on the mood of our people, encouraging them to be active.

RESULTS.

In the case of the above, the solution of this problem is of great theoretical and practical importance. It is known that the place and role of plants in nature and human life is

huge, they are not only food, clothing, building materials, but also a necessary source for some sectors of the economy. It is important to take an inventory of flora, including ornamental species, and to study their biological properties to determine their potential.

Despite the limited area of the Fergana Valley, in this area we find a rich and colorful variety of ornamental plants [4, 5, 6]. In view of the above, the study of ornamental plants of Fergana region and cities, the development of theoretical and practical bases for their effective use and protection, the relevance of the topic of our dissertation. There are 143 ginneries in Fergana, 143 ginneries in Fergana, and a number of refineries in the valley, as well as a number of refineries in Kokand and Margilan. In addition, the population of Fergana region is densely populated in Uzbekistan. The territory of Fergana region covers 6.7 thousand km² or 1.5% of Uzbekistan and makes up 11% of the country's population.

DISCUSSION.

According to the sanitary-hygienic norms of residential areas, 10% of the area should be alleys, parks and gardens. For a healthy generation, which is being held on a large scale in our country, such things as landscaping are also important. Our people have always grown beautiful, fragrant and beautiful plants. Such plants as roses, basil, jambul, potatoes, tulips, peonies, lilies of the valley and others have long been known.

It is said that as early as the 4th century BC, our people were engaged in the cultivation of ornamental trees, shrubs and beautiful flowers in gardens and alleys. This work has been going on for centuries and still is. It is known that our great ancestors Amir Temur, Ulugbek, Boburmirus visited the

famous gardens and resorts in Samarkand, Kabul and many other parts of India with great knowledge and taste, and built beautiful flower gardens there.

In fact, the Fergana Valley has long been famous for its beautiful gardens, lush greenery, hills and flowerbeds. This modern pamphlet has been prepared to continue the traditions of our people, who have masterfully grown plants in flower gardens, parks and camps. It describes the species composition and brief bioecological characteristics of plants that are common in urban areas, have long been cultivated and have recently been acclimatized. The importance of landscaping in cities and villages, the need to select and organize the species composition of plants for this purpose, as well as the effective use and protection of this flora are described.

It is known that the current stage of development of our society is characterized by the unprecedented growth of science and technology, the growth of the population of our planet. This process, in turn, is having a negative impact on nature, as man is creating huge hydro and nuclear power plants, artificial seas, supersonic aircraft, nuclear and icebreakers. There are huge areas of the planet being developed and included in agriculture. The thick forests of the African continent have been cut down and turned into savannas and semi-savannas. Today, the forests in the Amazon Basin, which serves as the planet's artificial lungs, are being wiped out. So now the planet's natural environment is changing. Changes in the environment, in turn, have led to a sharp decline in the range of a

number of species that grow there and fauna.

The importance of scenic species in the infrastructure of our cities is great. As a beautiful and unique symbol of nature, green plants have a positive effect on the mood and mood of workers, giving them creativity and aesthetic taste. Plants reduce dust and noise in cities and residential areas. Their phytocides kill viruses and bacteria that spread various diseases in the atmosphere.

According to our data, there are 104 species of ornamental plants in Fergana city and region, which belong to 87 genera and 41 families. Among them are Acer, Morus and others from the richest families Rosaceae, Oleaceae, Faloceae and Salixaceae. The ornamental species consists of 71 species of trees and 33 species of shrubs.

While maple, oak, linden, willow, willow, poplar, etc. still dominate in our cities and settlements, today the species of chestnut, silk acacia, paper tree, catalpa, pine have found their rightful place. has

CONCLUSION.

In the infrastructure of our cities there are rare and rare species such as ginkgo biloba, tulip tree, cypress. Also, ornamental shrubs decorate the squares of our cities: camel, biota, budleya, siren, kanna, yukka and others. It should be noted that among the ornamental plants we find many species of medicinal, essential oils, honey. In the hot and dry climate of the city and the regions of our region, the flora and fauna, including ornamental plants, are of great importance. They need to be used effectively and protected. May the next generation of us have a beautiful and prosperous homeland.

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